

The Connection from Beginning to Ending

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this paper is to show how one common thing can make a huge difference in someone's life and how in fact even though a lot of things seem to be misplaced or out of order, at the end of the day everything is just where it is supposed to be. We sometimes try and picture how everything would look like if we would have taken a different path. But who knows where that would have led us to? Life is an event filled with motion and is the pure fact that keeps us going. You either go with it or it takes over you...unless you find a way to stay ahead of it.

KEYWORDS: life, people, mind, events, order

CHAPTER I – WHERE IT ALL BEGINS

Life in general...no one knows for a fact when it all started or when it is going to end. We all have some ideas in our minds which we have formed based on what we have heard or what we have went through. Keeping up with everything is a time consuming aspect but it might be just what we need in order to not lose what we already have. "The beginning of world formation contains no assertion concerning the motive force that gives rise to it. There is emptiness and fullness in the universe. This universe is limitless with respect to space and time. World formation occurs when many multiform corpuscles are discharged from out of the infinite, the borderless reserve, as it were, of all world becoming and move into the great emptiness."¹

Just like the world in which we live is formed of multiple entities, some living and some not, our own lives are made up of the same things. What is important here is for one to realize the purpose each part has in it's life, as much as one can and make the most out of it. Living in this now, in this time, in this life is nothing if you don't make the best out of it even though what you have seems like almost nothing.

"Experience knows how within a lifetime, valued frameworks of interpretation are undermined by shifts in language and history. Yet experience also brings with it the lesson that no matter how bleak the loss of an interpretative framework might seem, negativity is al-ways of itself limited and never absolute. Negations as well as affirmations of meaning always leave more to be said."²

Like I've said...even though what we have seems like not much or almost nothing we don't know what it brings until we put it to good use. No matter the situation and the context we have to try. We have to be better than how we were when we started it. Every journey has a purpose although it may not seem like it. Every move that we make has it's consequences. And every consequence puts us in a different perspective. Everything, from when we start something until we finish it is what sums up the entire road that we take. And every spot that we don't fill could be what we needed to finish what we started. We have to search all that we can, and when we have done that we have to do it all over again just to make sure that we have covered everything. But all that effort is not in vain. Even though it may look like we are living the exact same thing we are not. Because after we have gone through it one time we will not be the same person and we will know how to look at things.

CHAPTER II – WHO WILL GET THERE FIRST

Everything in life is like a race. But we are not just going against what some may call faith. We are actually going against ourselves. And we have to beat us in order to win. "The persuasive speech which binds one man with another or even with himself in so intuitive and living a way that they seem inseparable from one another can nevertheless take on the rigid form of written

¹ Hans Georg Gadamer, *The Beginning of Knowledge*, Continuum, New York, 2002, p.91

² Nicholas Davey, *Unquiet Understanding. Gadamer's Philosophical Hermeneutics*, State University of New York, Albany, 2006, p.246

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relations.”³ In order to be better than who we were when we started this race we need to find allies to help us along the way. Forming bonds was never an easy task. Maintaining them is even harder. But what is life without some hard work? How can we truly become who we are meant to become if we don't use everything that we have?

“Are scientists so indifferent to the spectacle taking place before their eyes that they only see an ordinary, trivial scene? Are they preoccupied only by their next discovery or interested only in impressing their peers? Or is it perhaps the habit of seeing each problem end up in a solution, each experiment yield a result, that leads them to a kind of unquestioned certainty, to an absolute faith?”⁴ Just like every action has a reaction, every gesture leads somewhere. Every human is a piece of this puzzle called life. Indeed, the end result might be still a really big question but at least we took the first step towards it when we asked ourselves the first question...do we want to take this journey? Yes, of course we do. Because without it we would just be living in the past, letting things just pass by us and not to do anything about it. Not do anything for us. It might sound like a line that just come from a movie but we have to be our own person and in order to do that we need to find out where we are heading. Staying in the same place will do us no justice. Who knows what we could encounter along the way? Not even us if we don't start it.

“If we cannot attain lucid self-transparency, we can penetrate our inclination toward fallenness, become aware of escape routes into illusory safety, and have the courage to risk the restlessness of life in the recognition that putative points of repose are delusory.”⁵ Having the feeling that we are trapped somewhere should trigger in us the desire to overcome it. An ending should be looked at as a new beginning or as something that we need to overcome if it does not feel like it is the right ending. We cannot be sure that we have reached the end of our journey if we do not feel comfortable with who we are in that moment. Only when one becomes at peace why whom they are the journey has reached it's ending.

The road will be filled with so many questions and desired, losses and wins, hard times but also good one...making sure those happen is up to us. Facing everything with an open mind could help us access resources and answer that might have been left aside otherwise. Not everything in this world has an answer to it. That is for sure. But have to be able to look in the mirror, look into our own eyes and say out loud that we have indeed tried everything that we could have.

CONCLUSIONS

It is kind of funny, in some ways, that ever since we are little we are used to ask a million questions even though we might not really understand all the answers that we receive. Still we ask those questions, hoping that something will come along. As we go further down our life line we are asked to not address so many questions...like they are a bad thing. But we still have them even though we do not say them out loud. They still exist. They are still there. How we put them to use is up to us. But we have to use them. One thing is for sure. Everything is connected. From beginning to the end. And not just that. We are all connected. And we have proven that over and over again.

I do believe that even when we ask the inappropriate questions we are still doing something that will be useful as we go on with our journey. And once we have figured this out there won't be a single think capable of ripping the bonds that we have created with what is surrounding us or with who is surrounding us. Nevertheless, not to be mistaken...we may not find all the answers but at least we will be pleased with the fact that we know we did our best. Yes, some things are meant to left unsaid...but still we have asked ourselves those things. We have put our minds in motion. We have done something about it.

This journey called life and everything it has to offer will put us through things we may not imagine but in the end it will be worth it. There is no greater gift than finding yourself.

REFERENCES

- 1) Hans Georg Gadamer, *The Beginning of Knowledge*, Continuum, New York, 2002
- 2) Nicholas Davey, *Unquiet Understanding. Gadamer's Philosophical Hermeneutics*, State University of New York, Albany, 2006
- 3) Hans Georg Gadamer, *Truth and Method*, Continuum, London, 2004
- 4) *The Cambridge Companion to Gadamer*, Edited by Robert J. Dostal, Bryn Mawr College, Cambridge University Press
- 5) Roland Omnes, *Quantum Philosophy. Understanding and Interpreting Contemporary Science*, Princeton University Press, Princeton, 1999

³ Hans Georg Gadamer, *Truth and Method*, Continuum, London, 2004, p.551

⁴ Roland Omnes, *Quantum Philosophy. Understanding and Interpreting Contemporary Science*, Princeton University Press, Princeton, 1999, p.278

⁵ *The Cambridge Companion to Gadamer*, Edited by Robert J. Dostal, Bryn Mawr College, Cambridge University Press, p.175